

Scientific article

Enhanced Wind Farm Performance via Active Wake Control: A Steady-State Approach

Authors: Tim Dammann, Daan van der Hoek, Wei Yu, Jan-Willem van Wingerden

Published on: IEEE Conference Publication, 2025 American Control Conference (ACC)

Abstract: *Denser turbine spacing in wind farms leads to increased wake interactions, causing power losses when each turbine operates under its own greedy control scheme. To mitigate these effects, research is exploring strategies that consider the entire wind farm rather than singular turbines. The so-called helix approach has recently gotten significant attention from the research community. It aims to reduce wake losses through periodic individual pitch control. Wake steering on the other hand uses yaw actuation to laterally deflect the wake away from downstream turbines. In this paper, we adapt and validate a steady-state surrogate model to compute the time-averaged velocity field behind a wind turbine operating with the helix approach. The model is tuned using data from Large Eddy Simulations. We compare the helix model to wake steering and baseline operation in a wind farm case study, demonstrating that the helix approach offers promising benefits under specific wind conditions.*

Link to article: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/11107695>

SUDOCO is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101122256). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

